

Model to increase motivation and learning outcomes in learning history

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ABSTRACT

Value clarification technique (VCT) and teaching and contextual learning (CTL) are learning models that are rarely compared in history learning. Hence, the purpose of this study was to find: i) The differences in student learning outcomes using the VCT model and the CTL learning model; ii) Differences in student learning outcomes between the use of the VCT learning model and CTL learning model for students who have high learning motivation; iii) Differences in learning outcomes between the use of VCT and CTL learning models for students who have low learning motivation; and iv) The interaction effect between the use of learning models and students' learning motivation on learning outcomes. This study employed a quasi-experimental quantitative approach with a 2×2 factorial design. The data analysis technique used a two-way analysis of variance at a significance level (α) of 0.05. The population in this study was all students of class X of social science (IPS). The study's research showed that: i) There were significant differences in learning outcomes between students who used the VCT and CTL learning models; ii) There were differences in learning outcomes between the used of the VCT and CTL learning models for students who have high learning motivation; iii) There were differences in learning outcomes between the used of the VCT and CTL learning models for students who have low learning motivation; and iv) The used of the VCT and CTL learning models for students with high learning motivation was associated with better learning outcomes.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Every nation in the world has always found education to be a contentious issue. This is entirely understandable given that a nation's growth can mostly be gauged by how well its educational system is performing [1]. In order to build a quality, responsible, and fiercely competitive generation that can compete on a global scale, the quality and educational systems are anticipated to be a vehicle for improving and developing the quality of human resources [2]. For the Indonesian people, it is particularly important to be able to compete in a healthy way in order to raise the standard of education there.

Education universally means efforts to change humans to be smarter, and in Indonesian educational philosophy, education is an effort to educate the nation's life [3]. Efforts and strategies are needed that need to be implemented by schools to meet national education standards, especially by utilizing all potential, preparing work plans and programs according to needs, and encouraging all school components to improve their performance [4]. The central goal of national education is to develop the potential of students to become

human beings who believe in and fear God Almighty, have a noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, creative, and independent, and shape character and national civilization with good character [5]. Learning activities in schools are one of the ways that the quality of education can be improved [6].

Because of learning process can assist students obtain knowledge in real life, it is a crucial component of education in schools. In order for learning to take place, there must also be an attempt to stimulate, direct, and inspire students [7]. Aspects of increasing knowledge, skills, and attitudes are aspects of student competence that students must own due to learning outcomes expressed in observable and measurable behavior [8].

The 2013 curriculum introduces a new paradigm for education [9]. In order to accomplish educational objectives, the curriculum really serves as a guide for teachers and students on how to correctly conduct the teaching and learning process [10]. Hence, creating learning plans is a necessary skill for all educators to possess while creating a curriculum [11]. On the other side, the educational process gives pupils options that they can use to help them maximize their potential [12]. Through the Ministry of Elementary and Secondary Education, the Government of Indonesia held and established history as an important lesson in the 2013 curriculum [13]. Learning history aims to provide factual knowledge of history that every Indonesian citizen should know accordingly the level of education to encourage the results of character education [14].

It is essential for students to learn history since it can affect the nation's character and the characteristics of its citizens. By understanding the meaning and value of each historical event, students will be better able to prepare for the future rather than simply remembering dates. Learning about history can help kids develop a sense of history and mold their personalities so that they can represent it in modern society [15]. Learning history aims to develop knowledge and understanding of the journey of life of the people and nation of Indonesia and the world, manifesting behavior that is based on values and morals that reflect the character of oneself, society, and the nation, as well as developing international understanding and examining actual and global phenomena [16]. This ability is needed so that students can develop following the changing times [17].

Though students could study more actively and autonomously by examining the subject to be studied, the application of history education has not been maximized. One issue with teaching history in schools is that it can be challenging for pupils to participate actively because the process is still mostly controlled by the teacher and is still static and conventional [18]. Static nature might refer to the fact that history professors occasionally use only traditional methods, such as the lecture method, which consists solely of reading or repeating passages from books, without making any adjustments [19]. Students in traditional history classes are typically passive receivers of information (just listening to and writing down instructor descriptions are predominate) [20]. The ultimate effect is that many students receive marks that just meet the minimal completeness standards, are highly dependent on their teachers for subject matter, and often find learning to be boring.

The majority of the pupils have not participated actively in learning activities, according to the findings of observations made at state senior high school (SMA) 8 Ambon in March 2022 regarding the implementation of historical learning in the classroom. This methods of instruction place an emphasis on technical abilities including reading, listening, memorization, and taking notes. The bulk of learning activities still have poor student participation, which demonstrates this. Instructors focus more on the required target material than on the substance of the historical material itself, making history seem like a dry, rote subject that has no application to modern life. Much more evidence suggests that student learning outcomes fall short of the minimum completion standards set by the institution. The outcomes of the students' learning will suffer if the issue is not resolved.

The need for teacher innovation to solve this issue is great [21]. In implementing teaching tasks, ancient teachers were different from teachers today. The current era demands a teacher's creativity in carrying out his functions and responsibilities. Teachers are required to be able to use technology and be smart in knowing the learning situation [22]. The application of learning with a learning model that can engage students actively in the learning process is one of many factors that must be taken into account in the learning process to increase the quality and quality of learning outcomes [23].

The use of learning models can increase motivation and student learning outcomes [24]. The right learning model can make students pay more attention when the lesson progresses, learning conditions are more conducive, and student learning enthusiasm increases [25]. The success of learning and the accomplishment of learning objectives, which are reflected in some beneficial behavior changes, will be influenced by the accuracy with which a learning model is chosen. This assertion is consistent with Pattiasina's claim that a learning model can enable students to participate actively and collaborate in historical teaching and learning activities [26]. As a result, the best way to teach history in a way that will hold students' interest and attention is to use an active, inventive, creative, effective, fun, and more active learning model that unleashes their potential and helps them become more engaged in their studies. This

includes using the value clarification technique (VCT) model and the contextual teaching and learning (CTL) learning models.

VCT learning methodology analyzes existing values and instills them in pupils as a way to help students improve their morals/values and decide which values are regarded good in handling an issue [27]. The VCT according to Sanjaya can be described as a teaching method to help students locate and decide on a value that is thought to be good in handling a situation [28]. As successful people can investigate the values that must be taken without force, the VCT model can assist students in defining the values that they already possess [29]. Through value-based problem solving, conversations, discussions, and presentations, students are assisted in continually clarifying their personal values [30]. As a result, the VCT learning model is an effective educational strategy that teaches students how to identify, select, consider, make a decision about, and speak up for the values they want to defend [31]. In particular, VCT aims to support students in understanding their values and attitudes toward their goals as well as respecting and appreciating those values [32].

CTL is another educational strategy. The goal of the contextual learning model, according to Johnson, contextual teaching and learning is to give students the knowledge and skills they need to actively construct their understanding by assisting them in comprehending the meaning of the teaching materials and connecting them to real-world situations [33]. CTL learning is a learning concept to help students see meaning in the subject matter they are learning and how to relate it to the context of their daily lives in the context of their personal, social, and cultural environment [34]. Students can discover the significance of the material by connecting the two. When students actively choose, organize, touch, plan, investigate, seek out information, and draw conclusions from the actions they carry out themselves, they will see and understand the meaning of the subject matter [35].

The learning model, an external element, is one of several factors that affect the continuity and success of the learning process. The success of the learning process is determined by internal elements like learning motivation in addition to external influences [36]. In order to promote excitement for learning, learning motivation can be seen as the force that propels certain learning activities from both inside and outside the individual [37]. Learning motivation includes both efforts to accomplish learning objectives as well as being a motivating force for good results [38]. Motivation is necessary for the learning process since it will foster students' excitement for learning [39]. Students who want to study are more likely to be motivated to do so [40]. Pupils that are eager to learn will be interested in taking part in educational activities [41]. While this is going on, pupils who lack motivation for learning will be less passionate about studying and taking part in educational activities [42]. As a result, unmotivated pupils will most likely not achieve their academic potential [43]. Whether there is motivation to learn greatly affects the success of student learning. Success will be achieved if one has the will and drive to learn [44]. On the other side, students with low motivation will appear indifferent, get bored quickly, get discouraged easily, and try to avoid activities [45]. Motivational activities are closely related to self-actualization, so the motivation that most determine students' learning needs is learning to achieve high achievements [46]. As a consideration in this study, there have been previous researchers who have studied comparative learning models. But, what sets it apart from earlier research is that nobody has ever contrasted the VCT and CTL learning models to boost student motivation and learning outcomes.

This study aims to compare the learning outcomes of students using the VCT model and the CTL learning model. It also compares the learning outcomes of students using the VCT learning model and the CTL learning model for students with high and low learning motivation as well as the interaction effect between the use of learning models and students' learning motivation on learning outcomes.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This study used a quasi-experimental approach and is quantitative in nature. A factorial design was used in this study. This study was carried out in the second semester of class X social sciences (IPS) at state senior high school (SMA) 8 Ambon, Leitimur District, Indonesia on March 2022 until June 2022. The population for this study consisted of all students of class X IPS for the academic year 2021–2022, which encompassed four classes in total. The sampling method employed in this study is cluster sampling. In this study, class X B social science students from the state senior high school in Ambon, Indonesia, who received therapy using the VCT learning model, and class X A social science students from the same school, who received treatment utilizing the CTL learning model, served as the samples.

The research methodology is quantitative, and the primary data were gathered from learning outcomes assessments and questionnaires about learning motivation for history. Prior to testing and consideration from experts, the learning outcomes assessment tools and learning motivation questionnaires were validated. Cronbach's Alpha is used in the reliability test, and it must be higher than 0.6. Using the

product moment correlation technique, the validity of the questionnaire on the motivation of learning outcomes is determined. The item and test analysis (ITEMAN) program is used to conduct the validity test of the learning outcomes. The primary data collected were historical learning outcomes data using multiple-choice tests and learning motivation data using a questionnaire. The questions in the learning outcomes test regarding history learning materials are found in chapter 6 of class X and the questionnaire questions have been associated with learning motivation variables.

Learning outcomes assessments and questionnaires about motivation for learning were the instruments utilized in this study. The learning outcome test is a written multiple-choice exam with a total of 20 questions and four possible answers. Score 1 for the right answer and 0 for the incorrect one. A minimum score of 0 and a maximum score of 100 are determined by multiplying each number of right answers by 5. There were 22 statements make up the questionnaire used to assess learning motivation. The very good, good, sufficient, bad, and very poor categories make up the five score intervals on the Likert scale-based quantitative data measurement scale, with a minimum score of 22 and a maximum score of 110.

In this work, descriptive statistical analysis methods were used for data analysis. Maximum, minimum, mean, mode, and median values are part of descriptive statistical analysis. The data for this investigation were analyzed using a two-way ANOVA with 0.05. The normality test and homogeneity test were used to conduct the analysis precondition test. The hypothesis test is conducted once the analysis preparatory test is successful.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The description of student learning outcomes data was carried out twice, namely the initial test (pretest) before the learning activity process and the final test (posttest) or after the end of the learning process. Table 1 contains information on student learning outcomes for experiments 1 and 2. The data presented in Table 1 demonstrates that there are differences between the means of the learning results for students who take lessons using the VCT and CTL models on the pretest and posttest. The class that will participate in learning with the VCT model has an average pretest score of 61.03; the median score was 60; the mode was 60; the lowest score was 52; and the highest score was 75. The class that will participate in VCT learning has an average posttest score of 85.20; the median is 82; the mode is 79; the minimum score is 75; and the maximum score is 96.

Table 1. Description of data pretest and posttest student learning outcomes

	Mean	Median	Modus	Min	Max
Pretest VCT	61.03	60	60	52	75
Posttest VCT	85.20	82	79	75	96
Pretest CTL	64.80	62	66	55	76
Posttest CTL	80.25	78	75	75	92

The information in the table also reveals that the experimental group 2 class, which will learn using the CTL model, had a mean pretest score of 64.80, a median of 62, a mode of 66, the lowest score of 55, and the highest score of 76. The experimental group 2 class, who would participate in CTL learning, received an average posttest score of 80.25; median 78; mode 75; lowest score 75; and maximum score 92. Figures 1 and 2 are used to further explain the distribution of student learning outcomes using the VCT and CTL models.

Figure 1. Diagram of VCT class pretest and posttest results

Figure 2. Diagram of CTL class pretest and posttest results

Table 2 shows that there was an increase in student learning motivation on the VCT and CTL posttests. The minimum modus posttest value occurs in the CTL posttest which is 75 and the maximal modus posttest value occurs in the VCT posttest which is 82. The minimum posttest value occurs in the CTL posttest which is 70 and the maximal posttest value occurs in the VCT posttest which is 97.

Table 2. Description of pretest and posttest data on student learning motivation

	Mean	Median	Modus	Min	Max
Pretest VCT	68.39	69	69	55	85
Posttest VCT	85.14	81	82	76	97
Pretest CTL	69.62	69	66	59	84
Posttest CTL	80.21	75	75	70	90

Table 3 reveals that there are 11 students with low motivation and 15 students with strong motivation in the VCT class. There are 12 students with low motivation and 14 with strong motivation in the CTL class normality and homogeneity tests make up the prerequisite test. Tables 4 and 5 show the outcomes of the normality and homogeneity tests, respectively.

Table 3. Frequency distribution of learning outcomes motivation

Learning model	Student learning motivation		Amount
	Tall	Low	
VCT	15	11	26
CTL	14	12	26
Total	29	23	52

Table 4. Normality test results

Variable	Significance of Kolmogorov-Smirnov data group			
	VCT		CTL	
	Pretest	Posttest	Pretest	Posttest
Learning outcomes	0.4286	0.4299	0.3926	0.3808
Motivation to learn	0.4092	0.4095	0.3450	0.3402

Table 4's findings from the normalcy test demonstrate that the pretest and posttest significant values for the learning outcomes for motivation and history are both greater than 0.05. So, it can be said that the data's findings follow a normal distribution. The data presented in Table 5 demonstrates that the significant value of the findings of the Levenes test statistics is greater than 0.05. Hence, it can be said that the two groups' variance is homogeneous. The data presented in Table 6 indicates that the two-way ANOVA test determined that the average final learning outcomes for the VCT were 18.20 and the average for the CTL were 10.88, with an F_{hitung} of 7.711 and a significant value of 0.035. As a result of $p=0.035 < 0.05$, H_0 is disregarded, and H_a is approved. As a result, it was determined that employing the CTL learning model instead of the VCT learning model caused a shift in the learning outcomes.

Table 5. Homogeneity test results

Variable	Significance Levene test statistics	
	Pretest	Posttest
Learning outcomes	0.4009	0.4086
Motivation to learn	0.4850	0.8372

Table 6. ANOVA test results two path hypothesis 1 (comparison of the VCT learning model and CTL's effects on learning outcomes)

Learning model	Average	F _{hitung}	Sig.
VCT	18.20	7.711	0.035
CTL	10.88		

The data presents in Table 7 indicates that according to the results of the two-way ANOVA test, the average learning outcomes for students who have high learning motivation are 21.24, while the average learning outcomes for students who use the CTL learning model are 12.03, with F_{hitung} being 15.966 and the value of Sig being 0.000. H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted because the significance value is 0.000<0.05. It was determined that students with high levels of learning motivation experienced different learning results when using the VCT and CTL learning models.

Table 7. ANOVA test results two path hypothesis 2 (average of history learning outcomes in students with high learning motivation)

Learning model	Average	F _{hitung}	Sig.
VCT	21.24	15.966	0.000
CTL	12.03		

According to the data in Table 8, when the results of the two-way ANOVA test are calculated, the average learning outcomes using the VCT learning model for students who have low learning motivation are 10.12, while the average learning outcomes using the CTL learning models for students who have low learning motivation are 11.54, with F_{hitung} 4.082 and sig value of 0.040. H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted because the significance value 0.040>0.05. It was determined that students with low learning motivation experienced different learning results when using the VCT and CTL learning models.

Table 8. Results of two paths ANOVA hypothesis 3 (average of history learning outcomes in students with low learning motivation)

Learning model	Average	F _{hitung}	Sig.
VCT	10.12	4.082	0.040
CTL	11.54		

The data presented in Table 9 demonstrates that the two-way ANOVA test calculation yielded an F_{hitung} value of 8.287 and a sig value of 0.005. As a result, H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted because the significance value 0.040>0.05. The difference between learning outcomes utilizing VCT learning models and CTL learning models in students who have low learning motivation can therefore be explained by the interaction effect between students who utilize learning models and learning motivation. Figure 3 shows the connection between the learning model and motivation for learning on students' learning results in history classes.

Table 9. Results of two paths ANOVA hypothesis 4 (interaction of the use of learning models and learning motivation on learning outcomes)

Learning model	Motivation to learn	Average	F _{hitung}	Sig.
VCT	Tall	22.30	8.287	0.005
	Low	12.01		
CTL	Tall	12.15		
	Low	12.08		

Figure 3. Graph of interaction of the use of learning models and learning motivation on learning outcomes

The degree to which a student is motivated to learn affects their success. If there is incentive to learn, learning results will be at their best [47]. Lack of student motivation can hurt cognitive development and student achievement. Low motivation to learn needs to know the root cause so that students can find the right solution [48]. Learning motivation includes a desire for learning as well as an attempt to meet learning objectives. It also acts as a motivating factor for good results. So, it can be said that motivation will always decide how hard students work to learn so that their learning results would improve.

Students' learning results with high levels of learning motivation are significantly impacted by history lessons taught utilizing the VCT learning model. According to Ardika *et al.* [49], the VCT learning model presents a greater challenge for students who are highly motivated to learn because it gives them the opportunity to identify their own values and the values of others. It also enables them to use their analytical skills and emotional intelligence to comprehend their own feelings and behavioral patterns [50]. According to Nurfurqon *et al.* [51], when learning the VCT model, students are not just listening and taking notes; rather, they are encouraged to make connections between their knowledge and their ability to invite, involve, foster, and develop students' potential, especially developing potential attitudes. This is because the VCT model is successful in forming students' moral attitudes.

Students with low learning motivation can significantly improve their learning outcomes by adopting the CTL learning model to teach history. This, according to Syaifuddin *et al.* [52], is because low learning motivation students like the CTL learning model's phases, which are shorter and easier to follow than the VCT model's implementation. The learning process is conducted in the classroom with little involvement from the outside world, making it appear simpler and more ideal for students who lack learning desire. Low learning motivation causes students to get bored during learning activities fast, which makes them less interested in taking part in learning activities.

4. CONCLUSION

The study of the data and discussion of the findings led to the following conclusions. First, learning outcomes of students who study using the VCT model and those who study using the CTL approach are extremely different. Students perform better in history while utilizing the VCT learning model than when using the CTL learning model. Second, the VCT model and CTL model produce quite different learning outcomes for highly driven students. Pupils that are very motivated to study are better suited for the VCT learning style. Finally, the VCT model and the CTL model yield distinctly different learning outcomes for children who lack motivation. The CTL learning strategy is better suitable for students who lack learning motivation.

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